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Мафтунa Юлдашевна Рузикалова,
катта ўқитувчи, (PhD)
Қўқон давлат педагогика институти

ФАРҒОНА ВОДИЙСИНИНГ МЕЛИОРАЦИЯ ВА ИРРИГАЦИЯ ИШЛАРИ ТАРИХИДАН (1950 – 1970)

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Марказий Фарғонадаги ерларнинг мелиоратив ҳолатини яхшилаш ва суғориш жараёнлари, шунингдек, совет Иттифоқи ҳукуматининг пахта яккахокимлиги сиёсати принциплари асосида пахта етиштиришга ихтисослашган туманлар ва совхозларнинг ташкил этилиши натижасида пахта марказга етказиб бериш ва унинг салбий жиҳатлари бирламчи манбалар ёрдамида кўриб чиқилган. Фарғона, Андижон ва Наманган вилоятлари ҳудудларидаги кўриқ ерларни ўзлаштириш мақсадида 1953 йилда “Ферганаводстрой” махсус курилиш трести ва Фарғона колхозлараро совети ташкил этилгани ва мазкур ташкилотлар ёрдамида янги ерларни ўзлаштириш соҳасида кўп ишлар қилингани очиб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: қишлоқ хўжалиги, Марказий Фарғона, кўриқ ерлар, суғориш, давлат хўжаликлари, жамоа хўжаликлари, пахта яккахокимлиги, канал, мелиорация, “Ферганаводстрой”.

Мафтунa Юлдашевна Рузикалова,
(PhD) старший преподаватель

Кокандский государственный педагогический институт

ИЗ ИСТОРИИ МЕЛИОРАЦИОННЫХ И ИРРИГАЦИОННЫХ РАБОТ ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ДОЛИНЫ (1950 – 1970)

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются процессы мелиорации и ирригации земель в Центральной Фергане, а также организация районов и совхозов в этих районах, специализирующихся на хлопководстве, на принципах хлопковой монополии, политики Советского правительства и повышения предоставления хлопка центру и его отрицательные последствия анализируется с помощью первоисточников. Для освоения целинных степных земель на территории Ферганской, Андижанской и Наманганской областей в 1953 году были созданы Специальный строительный трест «Ферганаводстрой» и Ферганский межхозяйственный совет. При содействии этих организаций многое сделано в области освоения новых земель.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, Центральная Фергана, целинные земли, ирригация, совхозы, колхозы, хлопковая монополия, канал, мелиорация, “Ферганаводстрой”.

Maftuna Y. Ruzikulova,
(PhD) senior teacher
of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

FROM THE HISTORY LAND RECLAMATION AND IRRIGATION IN FERGHANA VALLEY (1950-1970)

ABSTRACT

In the article, the processes of reclamation and irrigation of lands in Central Ferghana, as well as, organization of districts and state farms in these areas specialized to cotton - growing on the principles of cotton monopoly policy of the Soviet Government and increase of provision of cotton to the center and its negative results are elucidated with the help of primary sources. In order to develop virgin steppe lands on the territory of the Ferghana, Andizhan and Namangan regions, in 1953 the “Ferghanavodstroy” Special Construction Trust and the Ferghana Inter-collective Farm Council were formed. With the assistance of these organizations has done a lot in the field of new land development.

Index terms: Agriculture, Central Ferghana, virgin lands, irrigation, state farms, collective farms, cotton monopoly, canal, land-reclamation, “Ferghanavodstroy”.

1. INTRODUCTION

All the historical period reclamation virgin lands have been played significant role in the world. Especially, in agriculture system of all countries around the world, as well as in ensuring the success of their economic development, irrigation and reclamation industry has always occupied an important place. In particular, the local agricultural irrigation traditions gradually evolved over the centuries, and the culture of irrigation, peculiar to each country, has obtained its own unique and individual characteristics. After getting Independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan in its irrigation system, as well as in every other sector of the country, huge radical reforms, entailing significant changes were made. Applying and exploring the modern methods and experience in reclamation received much attention, as the aim was to maintain the whole agriculture system through appropriate irrigation. The reason was that “...our agriculture is the irrigated agriculture. Huge channels, irrigation and drainage network in conjunction with irrigated fields form the united complex of the water and the land.” This fact alone suggests that the growing interest in history and culture of irrigation, developed by Uzbek people, requires the creation of deep and circumstantial research on their study.

2. METHODS

The article uses such methods as scientific, historical, comparative analysis, problem-periodic, objectivity, structural-systematic analysis and Oral history. The scientific significance of the research is reflected in the historical-comparative, problem-chronological methods of irrigation and land reclamation in the Central Ferghana region in 1950-1970.

In order to further develop and increase cotton production in the republic, the Soviet government began to pay special attention to the Ferghana Valley, which is a favorable area for irrigated agriculture. The development work began under the slogan as “Reclamation of the Steppe – the Mission for the Braves”.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is known that the 50–70s of the 20th century in Uzbekistan developed agriculture, including the cotton industry. In order to further develop the cultivation and multiplication of cotton in the republic, the Soviet government pays great attention to the territory of the Ferghana Valley. Which was considered the most suitable place for irrigated agriculture. In view of this, in the fifth five-year (1951-1955) plan, as well as in the resolutions of the IX Congress of the CP (B) of Uzbekistan (1952),

the main task was to further develop cotton growing, also expanding the irrigated land in the Fergana Valley and developing virgin lands.

The development of virgin and fallow lands become widespread, first, in the Fergana Valley. In the central district of Fergana – Buz, from 1950 to 1954, there were 2803 hectares of the land utilized; in 1953 – 1958, there were already 2960 hectares. Totally on the Valley from 1954 to 1960 there were developed 23100 hectares of the land, and from 1960 to 1965, there were more than 17,400 hectares utilized. In the developed areas, there were organized district of Buz, Yazyavan and Zadarya (now Mingbulok) specialized in cotton growing. This has a positive effect on the process of urbanization.

As stated above, the main tasks and in order to execute the orders of the Council of Ministers of the USSR, on September 16, 1952, an expanded resolution was adopted by the Central Committee of the KP (b) Uzbekistan and the government of the republic. It marked the first and second regular land development of the Fergana Valley, as well as practical tasks in the field of irrigation [1, p.26]. At the same time, the resolution emphasized the development from 1953 to 1958 of 36,000 hectares of arid desert lands of the Fergana Valley.

During these years, the Soviet government to make many decisions and decrees on the event of the development of new lands and the further development of the irrigation system of the Republic. In particular, since November 16, 1952, on the basis of the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party (B) of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR, work was carried out to irrigate new and virgin lands of Central Fergana on 65,000 hectares [2, 31]. By decree, this territory is distributed as follows:

1. Waterless steppes of Yazyavan and Red Tigin - 30,000 hectares;
2. According to the system of the Ulugnar Canal - 6,000 hectares;
3. According to the system named after the Okhunboboev Canal - 14,000 hectares;
4. Virgin and abandoned land with a total area of 15,000 hectares in three (Fergana, Andizhan and Namangan) regions.

The process of developing the territory of Central Fergana on a large scale began in 1953. At that time, its total area was 532.4 thousand hectares, and its net form was 363.7 thousand hectares [3, p.42]. From this until January 1, 1953, there was a need to develop 173.2 thousand hectares of land. Its 130.4 thousand hectares belonged to the Fergana region, and 42.8 thousand hectares of the Andizhan region [4, p.13].

The thesis points out that to ensure the rapid development of cotton growing the totalitarian government used to issue multiple series of decrees and orders. Naturally, as irrigation works in those decrees and orders received the most serious consideration. Among them, the decree of the USSR Council of Ministers and the CPSU Central Committee "On the further development of cotton production in Uzbek SSR on 1954 - 1958 years" from February 9, 1954, which planned the expansion of irrigated areas (600 thousand hectares, including the cotton fields on 300 ha.), significant land improvement and providing the rational use of water in the state and collective farms. The decision, along with the development of cotton production confirmed the increase of its monoculture policy in comparison with the previous years.

On January 23, 1959, the Central Committee of the CP of the Uz SSR and the Council of Ministers of the Uz SSR adopted a decree "On approval of the plan for construction works on reclamation and irrigation of lands in Central Fergana during 1959". According to it, the growth volume of the irrigated lands in the Central Fergana array was 13,000 hectares, in reality, it was executed at a rate of 10,230 hectares. In the decision, it was noted that during this year for the development and irrigation of Central Fergana land, from the planned for the construction funds of 186 685 thousand sum, it has been allocated and spent the amount of 105 750 thousand roubles from indivisible savings accounts of the public enterprises of Ferghana, Andizhan and Namangan regions, 55385 thousand roubles from the state budget, 23400 thousand roubles from the account of "Selhozcredit", and 2150 thousand sums from "Uzbekbirlashuv" fund accounts [5, p.3].

At the same time, the Soviet Government has created many artificial canals and pumping stations to provide water for hillside areas where the natural irrigation was not possible. Many

activities to improve and maintain their technical condition have been developed. On July 12, 1952 the Ministry of cotton production of the USSR issued a decree "On measures to improve the technical condition of the Big Fergana Canal named after Stalin"[6, p.32]

The main objective pointed here was the extensive use of water resources in order to improve the technical condition of the channel, and the development of irrigation of the Fergana Valley. In accordance with this decree, the Minister of Water Resources of the UzSSR and the Chief Operating Manager of the Big Fergana Canal received the order, in the term of 3 months in cooperation with the local organizations, to optimize the staff of the management, and to provide the controlling and hydro-technical areas with highly skilled professionals. During 1953, it was entrusted to make cleaning of the Big Fergana Canal in the area from the dam of Kuyganyar until the Asaka siphon, and complete cleaning of the South Fergana Canal.

In 1955-1959, in the Fergana Valley they built 9 pumping stations, providing water for 10 thousand hectares. At the same time, the collector-drainage system's length has reached 37 thousand km. In order to avoid the disappearance of the filtered water, during seven years (1959-1965) in the areas with water shortage, 545 km of water channels were covered by concrete.

Frequency and long-lasting of irrigation activities in the Fergana valley led to further strengthening the policy of cotton monoculture, and how difficult it was is possible to guess from the slogans made in the spirit of colonization, such as "Development of the Steppe – the Mission for the Braves" to motivate people to do the forced labor. The cultivated area allowed to develop cotton production and to increase the amount of harvest. At the steppes on the developed areas cotton growing districts and state farms were created, residential complexes for the population were built. Housing construction has created favorable conditions for the people previously living in densely populated areas. In connection with the annual increase in the number of state farms, specialized in cotton, cotton production also has grown each year. However, unfortunately, most of the grown cotton was taken away to the Center.

In order to develop virgin steppe lands on the territory of the Fergana, Andizhan and Namangan regions, in 1953 the Ferganavodstroy Special Construction Trust and the Fergana Inter-collective Farm Council were formed. With the assistance of these organizations has done a lot in the field of new land development. In Central Fergana from 1953 to August 1, 1956, the following funds were spent for capital construction works [7, p.107].

Table №1.

**Consumption of funds for capital construction works in Central Fergana (1953-1956).
(Taking into account thousand rubles).**

№	Years	From farm fund	Collective	From the state budget
1.	1953	16574		17788
2.	1954	45330		18062
3.	1955	53295		15328
4.	1956	21660		4422
Total		136859		55600

On February 26, 1957, the Central Committee of the Communist Party (Bolsheviks) of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR adopted resolution No. 99. According to this resolution, on March 18 of this year, the Ministry of Agriculture, number No. 55, issued an order "On the strengthening of irrigation and land development Central Fergana "[8, p.57]. On the basis of this order, the irrigation and development plan for the farms of Central Fergana's land in the period 1956 - 1961 was 80.0 thousand hectares of virgin and fallow lands, including these lands in the oblasts distributed in the following way [9, p.59]: in the Fergana region 32.0 thousand hectares, in the Andijan region - 28.0 thousand hectares. and in the Namangan region - 20.0 thousand hectares [10, p.23].

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the lands of Central Fergana irrigation and reclamation work has developed at a high level, as well as agriculture, including cotton growing. There were positive aspects, but there were also negative consequences for this. In this place of work on the development of land lasted from 1953 to 1973. During these years, the tasks of the development of virgin and fallow lands, for this purpose, the allocation of funds and the decision of the government in many places were not fulfilled.

In turn, the development of new lands year after year increased the cultivation of cotton. This process has further strengthened cotton autocracy in agriculture. In the expansion of cotton growing, the sense of proportion was not observed, scientific recommendations were not ignored, crop rotation was not disturbed, and so on. As a result, the complexity in the development of new lands was grossly violated, ignoring the multi-sectoral development of the public economy contributed to the forced penetration of cotton monoculture into the economy.

References:

1. Gofurov A. Economical issues of development irrigation and land reclamation. –Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1974. -P.26. (Ғофуров А. Ирригация ва мелиорацияни ривожлантиришнинг иқтисодий проблемалари. -Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 1974.-С.26. (In Uzbek)
2. Andizhan province State Archive, fund-608, collected volume-1, list-932, p. 31. (In Russian)
3. Andizhan province State Archive, fund-608, collected volume-1, list-935, p. 42.
4. Fergana province State Archive, fund-1151, collected volume-1, list-100, p.13.
5. Namangan province State Archive, fund-275, collected volume. 1, list-1341, p. 3.
6. Andizhan province State Archive, fund-608, collected volume-1, list-932, p. 32.
7. Andizhan province State Archive, fund-619, collected volume-1, list-113, -p.107.
8. Fergana province State Archive, fund-1151, collected volume-1, list-87, -p. 57.
9. Fergana province State Archive, fund-1151, collected volume-1, list-87,-p.59.
10. Fergana province State Archive, fund-1151, collected volume-1, list-89, -p.23.
11. Аминова М. М. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ВОСПИТАНИИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ //Интернаука. – 2020. – №. 22-2. – С. 51-52.
12. Mutalibovna A. M. INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO MODERN YOUTH EDUCATION.
13. Rao, Parupalli Srinivas, et al. "An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal." (2011): 10-14.
14. Ruzikulova M. The history of irrigation in central Ferghana (1950-1970) //Scientific research results in pandemic conditions (COVID-19). – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 02. – С. 117-121.
15. Рузикулова М. Ю. Марказий Фарғонада суғориш иншоотлари ва давлат хўжаликларининг ташкил этилиши тарихи (XX асрнинг 50-70-йиллари мисолида) //Взгляд в прошлое. – 2020. – Т. 3. – №. 7.

ЎТМИШГА НАЗАР

3 МАХСУС СОН

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